

Effect of Chlorohexidine and Listerine mouthwash on absorbable sutures in third molar surgery - A Prospective Study

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ABSTRACT

Background

The primary goal of suturing the incisions is to approximate tissues, control hemorrhage, and assist the primary healing process to its natural appearance as much as possible. Sutures play a major role in maintaining the tissue integrity of surgical wounds. Both absorbable and non-absorbable suture materials are available for wound closure. Absorbable sutures do not require removal and save time and reduce patient anxiety postoperatively. The common practice for oral surgeons to prescribe antiseptic mouthwashes following surgical procedures, but the effect of various antiseptic mouthwashes on sutures has not been entirely tested.

AIM

This study was done to evaluate the effect of Chlorohexidine and Listerine mouthwash on absorbable sutures in third molar surgery.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This prospective study was conducted at Saveetha Dental College, Chennai - Tamil Nadu, in the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery. The sample size was calculated using the G-power software with a confidence interval of 95%. After the surgical removal of third molar was done and 3.0 vicryl was used to approximate the tissues. Using simple randomization, sixty participants were divided into 3 groups such that chlorohexidine, listerine and warm saline mouthwash was prescribed for patients in group A, B and C respectively and weekly follow up was done for retention of sutures.

Results

The mean longevity of vicryl calculated based on knot pull test for tensile strength, in patients that used chlorohexidine was 24.5 days, with a range of 14-28 days, listerine was 23.7 with range of 14-35 and of warm saline mouthwash was 22.5 days with a range of 14-28 days.

Conclusion

From our study we conclude that, there was a significant difference in resorption rate of suture material and thus Chlorohexidine and Listerine found to have no appreciable effect on vicryl. Hence depending on the availability and cost effectiveness and surgeon's choice, both the mouth washes as safe to be used after third molar surgery.

BACKGROUND

Wound repair is a highly intricate and meticulously coordinated process that encompasses several distinct phases: inflammation, cell proliferation, matrix deposition, and tissue remodeling [1]. The primary objective of suturing is to approximate tissues, control hemorrhage, and assist the primary healing process to its natural appearance as much as possible [2]. In the context of oral surgery, the behavior of sutures is affected by various factors including the quality of the surrounding tissues, the presence of saliva, and the specific microbiota in the area. The materials are under continuous mechanical forces from mastication, speech, facial expressions, and alteration in pH levels, bacterial proteolytic enzymes, saliva etc. affect the absorption rate/tensile strength of material [3]. Tensile strength is a factor in the longevity of suture material. The ratio of the greatest stress that a suture can sustain without breaking to the initial cross-sectional area of the specified material is known as the tensile strength of the material.[4] Sutures serve as a vital connection between internal and external tissue layers, significantly influencing the overall quality of the wound healing process.

Nonabsorbable monofilament sutures, such as ethilon (nylon) and prolene, are known for causing minimal inflammatory reactions, sliding smoothly through tissues, and need to be removed. These characteristics make them particularly well-suited for running intradermal stitches. Among absorbable suture materials, monocryl and vicryl sutures have been widely used due to their various physical and biomechanical features including their degradation rate, reduction of adherent bacteria biofilm, and better healing response [5-7]. However, a notable disadvantage of absorbable suture is its predictability of resorption due to effect of various factors mentioned above, which can sometimes compromise the stability of the closure. Absorbable sutures do not require removal, save time and reduce patient anxiety postoperatively due to which it is commonly used intraorally. But understanding of absorption rate and factors affecting it, is essential to the surgical procedures [8,9].

Third molar surgery involves inflammation of the surgical flaps during wound healing which may exert a certain degree of tension on wound edges and cause subsequent bridging of flap margins. Thus, it is of utmost importance to maintain the approximate wound margins via sutures that have an acceptable level of tensile strength with minimal tissue reaction. For optimal wound healing following dental surgery and to avoid postoperative problems, maintaining good oral hygiene is crucial. Traditional antiseptic mouthwashes such as Chlorohexidine, Listerine are frequently used to care for one's mouth, but that could potentially affect the sutures by weakening or strengthening their tensile strength [10]. In recent years, several studies report that a suture's tensile strength may be affected by specific solutions or consumed fluids.

An experimental study shows a progressive loss of tensile strength in Vicryl suture materials when subjected to saliva, bovine milk, and soy milk over a period of 35 days [2]. Saliva-soaked specimens show a more rapid loss of tensile strength than the other soaking liquids [3]. Another study reports that Vicryl shows better breaking strength compared to natural sutures. This is especially evident after immersion in physiological and acidic pH solutions [11]. Moreover, a recent report suggests that antiseptic solutions have an impact on the failure load of sutures used [12]. According to in vitro study, the tensile strength of seamcryl suture material was found to be higher in the clove-uni stevia mouthwash group than in the nilavembu silver nanoparticles mouthwash [13]. While rate of loss of irradiated polyglactin 910 (vicryl rapide) from the mouth shows no effect of chlorohexidine on rate of loss of suture [14]. Thus, this study aims to evaluate the effect of Chlorohexidine and Listerine mouthwash on absorbable sutures in third molar surgery.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design and setting

This prospective study was conducted at Saveetha Dental College, Chennai - Tamil Nadu, in the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery. The sample size was calculated using the G-power

software with a confidence interval of 95%. Using simple randomization, sixty participants were included in the study which requires surgical removal of third molar and they were divided into three groups.

Inclusion criteria

The patient age group was selected between 18 and 70 years. Both sexes were included in the study.

Exclusion criteria

Smokers, alcoholics, patients with a history of allergy to chlorohexidine and listeria mouthwash, presence of abscess were excluded from the study.

Surgical procedure

All procedures were done under local anesthesia, twenty patients were selected for the group A (Chlorohexidine), twenty patients for the group B (listerine) and twenty patients for the group C (warm saline). After local anesthetic injection (2% lidocaine with 1:80,000 epinephrine), modified wards incision was given, flap raised, surgical removal of third molar was done and 3.0 vicryl was used to approximate the tissues [FIGURE 1]. The technique used was the standardized two clock wise, one anti clock wise and one clock wise to tie the surgical knot. Chlorohexidine, Listerine and warm saline mouthwash was prescribed for patients in group A, B and C respectively and weekly follow up was done for retention of sutures [FIGURE 2]. Standard post-operative instructions and medications were given. The patients were asked to brush their teeth the way they are used to but to avoid the surgery site. They were also advised not to take sticky food because this could dislodge the sutures.

Outcome parameters

Clinical parameter that was assessed in the study the mean longevity of vicryl calculated based on knot pull test for tensile strength when assessed on day 7, 14 and 21.

Statistical analysis

Data will be entered into the Excel sheet. Data will be analyzed using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) 22.0 version, IBM Corp. Descriptive statistics will be performed. Categorical data will be compared using the Chi-Square test and continuous data between the groups will be compared using the unpaired 't' test or Mann-Whitney U test. The level of significance will be set at $P \leq 0.05$.

RESULTS

A total of 60 sutures were placed, 20 of whom used chlorhexidine. In 1 case suture got removed on 7th day, in another 2 cases the suture was lost at 21 days and rest at 14 days. 20 of whom used listerine, 1 got removed on seventh, 3 cases the suture was lost at 21 days and rest at 14 days. While the 20 of whom who used warm saline mouthwash, in 5 cases suture got removed on 7th day and rest in 14 days. Thus, the mean longevity of vicryl calculated based on knot pull test for tensile strength, in patients that used chlorhexidine was 24.5 days, with a range of 14-28 days, listerine was 23.7 with range of 14-35 and of warm saline mouthwash was 22.5 days with a range of 14-28 days.

The effect of chlorhexidine on the rate of suture loss

The mean number of days to suture loss was slightly more but not significantly more in the chlorhexidine users (14.35days, range 7–21) than in the control group (12.6days, range 7–14).

The effect of listerine on the rate of suture loss

The mean number of days to suture loss was slightly more but not significantly more in the chlorhexidine users (14.7 days, range 7–21) than in the control group (12.6 days, range 7–14).

DISCUSSION

The surgeon wants a combination of high tensile strength, easy handling, low to no tissue reactivity and minimal risk of infection [15]. The material should be clearly visible in the tissue and should consist of non-capillary, non-allergenic and non-carcinogenic material [16]. In biological terms, suture must be functional until the complete epithelium develops with sufficient tensile strength to stand alone. Beyond this, the suture acts as a foreign body and may impair healing potential due to food lodgement. Knowledge of the time of the events in the healing of the oral tissues is therefore important [10]. During the acute inflammatory phase of wound healing, the tissues do not gain appreciable tensile strength, but depends solely upon the closure material to hold them in approximation [17]. However, stronger or more tensile suture material is not always better, as the thread caliber must be increased and unintentional strangulation of the tissue may occur, which on the one hand endangers blood circulation and possibly also increases inflammatory reactivity [18]. A study shows vicryl sutures retained more than two-thirds of their original tensile strength, while monocryl sutures retained around one-third of the original strength. In another study, a significant difference in tensile strength between the 5-0 and 4-0 vicryl was observed, favouring 4-0 vicryl sutures at day 10, but a negligible difference was noted at day 14 [19]. Another study documented the mean survival of vicryl in the oral cavity to be 28 days [20]. The findings of this study do not agree with this observation, which may perhaps be due to the lower number of patients the authors studied. Vicryl loses half of its tensile strength in few weeks and could be used only when enough healing is expected within that period.

It was noted that resorbable suture (vicryl) used in procedures done under local anesthesia for third molar surgery has slightly shorter resorption time or faster resorption rate without the use of mouthwash. Chlorhexidine mouthwash slightly increased the time but was found to have statistically not significant effect on absorption time of the sutures. The expected reason for this is that mouthwash only stays in the oral cavity for a limited period of time rather than completely soaked in it, as well as other factors such as food, saliva, toothpaste etc. are also responsible to affect the tensile strength of suture material.

Limitations of the study

The limitations of the study were that, it was conducted on a small population with limited parameters and under different conditions. In further studies, the sample size has to be increased. The study was also conducted at a single center, further studies must be conducted at multiple centers.

CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this study to ascertain whether the use of mouthwash have any effect on the resorption rate of suture material or not is successful in stating that chlorhexidine and listerine mouth washes were found to have no significant effect on both suture absorption time when compared with normal saline mouthwash. Hence depending on the availability and cost effectiveness and surgeon's choice, both the mouth washes as safe to be used after third molar surgery.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Author Contributions

All authors have reviewed the final version to be published and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Concept and design: Rajprakash Bhaskaran, Manan Gupta, Murugesan Krishnan, Santhosh P. Kumar

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Disclosures

Human subjects: Consent was obtained or waived by all participants in this study. Institutional Human Ethics Committee of Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals issued approval IHEC/SDC/OMFS-2301/24/029. **Animal subjects:** All authors have confirmed that this study did not involve animal subjects or tissue. **Conflicts of interest:** In compliance with the ICMJE uniform disclosure form, all authors declare the following: **Payment/services info:** All authors have declared that no financial support was received from any organization for the submitted work. **Financial relationships:** All authors have declared that they have no financial relationships at present or within the previous three years with any organizations that might have an interest in the submitted work. **Other relationships:** All authors have declared that there are no other relationships or activities that could appear to have influenced the submitted work.

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